

Comparative analysis of Rostov-2 VVER-1000 HZP steady state with HELIOS, DYN3D and Serpent codes at Framatome

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ABSTRACT

The Rostov-2 VVER 1000 benchmark specification is used for hot zero power steady-state assembly-wise and pin-wise analysis. The calculations are performed with the HELIOS/DYN3D neutronic toolchain, which is one of the toolsets used at Framatome for VVER type pressurized water reactors analysis. Reference calculations are conducted with Serpent, a Monte Carlo-based code. Additionally, taking the place of HELIOS, Serpent is employed for neutron two-group constant generation for the DYN3D core simulator. ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library is used in the studies. The research comprises the determination and comparison of the radial and axial power distribution on the assembly, as well as pin level. The results show good agreement of both HELIOS/DYN3D, and Serpent/DYN3D toolchains with the reference Serpent outcome. The research constitutes further elements of the ongoing verification and validation of HELIOS/DYN3D toolset at Framatome.

Keywords: Rostov-2, VVER-1000, Helios, DYN3D, Serpent

1. INTRODUCTION

As a result of the current nuclear renaissance, as well as the increase of the computational resources potential, the development and the use of the validated neutron transport codes, which are characterized by suitable accuracy and good reality reflection is highly desirable. The use of validated and verified nuclear engineering tools is crucial for obtaining reliable results and to deepen the knowledge of how nuclear reactors behave under normal operation. This aspect is also significant in terms of safety analysis required by safety authorities. However, in many cases, including commercial VVER type reactors, the number of publicly available data remains limited. To address this issue, OECD/NEA on initiative of *Expert Group on Multi-Physics Experimental data, Benchmarks and Validation* developed and published a couple of VVER-related benchmark activities. The latest one, based on the measurements conducted in unit 2 of the Rostov Nuclear Power Plant (Rostov-2 NPP) is entitled “Benchmark on reactivity compensation of boron dilution by stepwise insertion of control rod cluster into VVER-1000 core” [1]. This benchmark report contains a unique dataset of a VVER-1000 NPP, suitable for both code-to-measurement, as well as code-to-code analysis, as done in the presented studies. The aim of the research was to conduct comparative calculations to evaluate the HELIOS/DYN3D toolset, which is used at Framatome for VVERs’ core analysis. It forms a part of an ongoing VVER-dedicated toolset validation and verification (V&V). Previously conducted and reported studies also addressed code-to-code V&V of HELIOS/DYN3D [2], as well as the QUADRIGA(HELIOS)/ANDREA code sequence [3] to Serpent reference results but using the X2 VVER-1000 benchmark dataset from Khmelnytskyi NPP [4].

2. ROSTOV-2 FRESH CORE MODEL

The Rostov-2 core is equipped with 163 hexagonal fuel assemblies (FAs) of TVS-2M type. At the beginning of the cycle under consideration, 5 types of FAs with uranium/uranium-gadolinium fuel are placed in the core. The individual FAs differ from each other in terms of U-235 enrichment, which varies from 1.3% to 4.0%, number of burnable absorber rods in each of the assemblies (0, 6 or 9 rods per assembly) and the burnable absorber content in the rods (0%, 5% or 8%). Each of the FAs has 12 spacer

grids located in the active core, which in our code-related comparison are not modelled individually, but their material is diluted homogeneously in the entire moderator material. To compare the impact of the spacer grids' modeling on the axial and radial power distribution, three different spacer grid models are under consideration, and the results will be presented in a follow-up publication, as a complement to this work. For this study, the core is at beginning of cycle, i.e., all assemblies are at burnup zero.

3. CODES AND METHODS

One of the neutronic toolchains, which is used at Framatome for VVERs comprises the HELIOS-2 [5] code (developed by Studsvik Scandpower) applied for cross-section generation, and the DYN3D [6] (developed by HZDR) core simulator, which can perform both stationary and transient simulations. The state-of-the-art neutronic calculations are performed with the Serpent [7] Monte Carlo code (developed by VTT Technical Research Centre), which is also used for two-group constant generation for the DYN3D core simulator. All simulations apply the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library. As only one hot zero power (HZP) all-rods out (ARO) steady state of the reactor is considered, only one set of core parameters is applied for both the Monte Carlo calculations, and the two-group constants generation with HELIOS and Serpent, Table I.

Table I. Parameters of the simulations and cross-section generation.

Fuel temperature (K)	Moderator density (kg/m ³)	Boron concentration (g/kg)
553	764.84	6.971

3.1. Serpent reference model

The reference calculations performed with Serpent are based on the detailed heterogeneous 3D core model following the data provided by the benchmark specification [1]. To optimize the calculation time and available computational resources, and essentially to minimize the power distribution asymmetry, which arises from the statistical nature of Monte Carlo transport, the results of five independent Serpent runs were averaged. In each simulation 2000 active, and 250 inactive cycles with 10⁶ neutron histories have been simulated. Assembly-wise and pin-wise power distribution analysis have been performed for the following code-to-code studies.

3.2. HELIOS/DYN3D neutronic toolset

HELIOS-2.04.00 version with 173 neutron and 48 gamma energy groups based on the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library is employed for two-group constants generation then applied in the DYN3D core simulator. For the cross-section generation the 60° and 120° symmetry of hexagonal-shaped FAs was used, Figure 1. Periodic and mirror boundary conditions on the intra-assembly and outer-assembly boundaries were applied, respectively.

The symmetry of the core's surroundings enables to distinguish five geometrical sectors of radial reflector, which are sufficient to cover and recreate the whole radial reflector. Each model consists of a hexagonal-shaped zone of interest, mostly comprised of a part of steel baffle with cooling channels, and six surrounding assembly-shaped zones made of FAs and more external parts of the radial reflector. The example of one out of five radial reflectors' model is depicted on Figure 2 (left). The region of interest is the one located as a middle hexagon with caption R1. On the FA sides, reflective boundary conditions were applied, on the other hand on the inert (non-fission) regions, black boundary conditions.

Since HELIOS is a two-dimensional code, axial reflectors have to be recreated following the radial structures. Axial reflectors, both at top and bottom, are modelled as two (active and inactive) neighboring 60° triangular sectors of assembly. The active and inactive parts correspond to an FA (driver) and the top/bottom reflector region made of layers of suitable materials, respectively, Figure 2

(right). The more precise procedure of the cross-section generation with HELIOS for DYN3D core simulator, as well as the models of all five radial reflectors with their surroundings can be found in previously published papers related to VVER-1000 V&V [2, 3].

Figure 1. HELIOS assembly models for cross-section generation.

Figure 2. HELIOS radial (on the left) and axial (on the right) reflectors' models for cross-section generation.

3.3. Group constant generation with Serpent for DYN3D core simulator

As was originally intended, Serpent code can be also used for few-group constant generation for deterministic steady-state and transient nodal diffusion codes [8]. Based on an already created 3D heterogeneous core model, 2D detailed models of all FA types were prepared separately. Since the geometry of the FAs here is not limited to only its part using the present symmetry, reflective boundary conditions are applied at all six outer surfaces of FA. Intermediate multi-group constants considering the leakage-corrected critical spectrum have been generated with the use of fundamental mode calculation (FM). The diffusion coefficient was obtained using the cumulative migration method (CMM).

In case of the radial reflector, the five exactly same hexagonal zones as with HELIOS have been homogenized from the 2D full core model. The homogenization areas are pointed out as yellow hexagons on the radial quarter-core cross section in Figure 3. The two-group constants have been prepared for each individual region running one 2D full core simulation. The FM CMM calculation mode is turned off here, additionally the assembly discontinuity factors (ADF) option has been turned on to evaluate the discontinuity factors for each hexagon surface.

For the axial reflectors, a 3D assembly-based model containing the top and bottom reflector have been created. Reflective and vacuum boundary conditions are applied for radial and axial boundaries, respectively. The layout of the axial reflectors is marked yellow on the assembly axial cross section, Figure 3. Here, both FM CMM, as well as ADF options are switched off.

In each case, the two-group constants with a boundary between them at 0.625 eV are calculated using at first Serpent default 70-group structure, as a micro group structure.

Figure 3. Serpent radial and axial reflectors' models for cross-section generation.

3.4. DYN3D model

The DYN3D core model comprises 163 homogenized fuel assemblies and 48 assembly-shaped radial reflectors which surround the active core. The active core is divided into 20 equal-sized planes. Additional two same-height planes are located, one above and one below the active core which constitute the top and bottom axial reflectors, respectively. Two separated DYN3D calculations were performed, for which the two-group constants were generated with two different approaches described in paragraphs 3.2 and 3.3.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Assembly-wise power distribution

Table II indicates the results of the criticality calculation for hot zero power steady-state, obtained for the core parameters mentioned in Table I. Additionally, Table II includes the assembly power peaking factors and the information in which FAs these values occur. The results reached with HELIOS/DYN3D and Serpent/DYN3D toolchains, are 0.79% and 0.29% higher than Serpent values, respectively. One can notice that the FAs with the highest power results coincide. That FAs numbers 9, 11, and 45 lack in the Serpent result arises from the statistical nature of the code. The values for the homologue FAs are 1.393, 1.394 and 1.394, respectively.

Table II. HZP critical state results.

	k_{eff} (-)	$\Delta\rho$ (pcm)	FA power peaking factor (assembly N ^o)
Serpent	1.00023 (\pm 0.00005)	23.0	1.395 (29)
HELIOS/DYN3D	0.998335	-166.8	1.406 (9, 11, 29, 45)
Serpent/DYN3D	0.998600	-140.2	1.399 (9, 11, 29, 45)

Figures 4 and 5 present the assembly power distribution with values normalized to the averaged FA power and color coding according to absolute differences of the results obtained with HELIOS/DYN3D and Serpent/DYN3D neutronic toolchains in comparison to Serpent. The minimum and maximum differences, with indication in which FA this discrepancy occurs and root-mean squared differences (RMS) in FAs are presented in Table III.

Figure 4. HELIOS/DYN3D toolset and Serpent assembly-wise radial power distribution comparison.

Figure 5. Serpent/DYN3D toolchain and Serpent assembly-wise radial power distribution comparison.

Table III. Assembly-wise power distribution comparison to Serpent results

	MIN difference (FA N ^o)	MAX difference (FA N ^o)	RMS (-)
HELIOS/DYN3D	-0.014 (8, 53)	+ 0.020 (39, 57)	0.0091
Serpent/DYN3D	-0.011 (16, 52)	+ 0.014 (30, 39, 57)	0.0073

4.2. Axial power distribution

The axial power distribution along the active core for all three numerical approaches with their difference determined for each plane out of 20 defined axial layers is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Axial power distribution comparison.

4.3. Pin-wise power distribution

Figure 7 depicts the pin power distribution in FA number 29, for which the highest assembly power peaking factor occurs. The presented results are normalized to the average pin power in the core. It can be noted that most of the results fall within the range of 1.2 to 1.6. The highest values are presented in the outermost ring of pins slightly towards the right from the center of the FA. The pins with value '0.00' are the guide tubes for control rods, whereas pins with values around 0.3 (indicated with blue) are the pins with uranium-gadolinium fuel. The absolute differences between the Serpent reference results and the HELIOS/DYN3D and Serpent/DYN3D simulations can be found in Figure 8, on the left and on the right, respectively. The color coding indicates the absolute differences between both values. The minimum and maximum differences in relation to Serpent results and the pin of the occurrence, as well as RMS pin power differences are collected in Table IV. The pins with the minimum and maximum difference values are located in the same assembly position, for both HELIOS/DYN3D and Serpent/DYN3D simulations. It is worth noticing that the pin in which the largest codes difference can be observed (approx. 5.4% of relative difference) is not the pin with the highest power in the assembly, for which the difference is up to 0.002.

Figure 7. Pin power distribution of assembly N°29 with Serpent (on the right), HELIOS/DYN3D (in the middle) and Serpent/DYN3D (on the left).

Figure 8. Assembly N°29: pin-wise power absolute difference between Serpent and HELIOS/DYN3D (on the left) and Serpent/DYN3D (on the right) results.

Table IV. Fuel assembly N°29: pin-wise power distribution comparison to Serpent results.

	MIN difference (pin N°)	MAX difference (pin N°)	RMS
HELIOS/DYN3D	-0.029 (78)	+ 0.084 (266)	0.0141
Serpent/DYN3D	-0.027 (78)	+ 0.091 (266)	0.0125

5. CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents validation of the HELIOS/DYN3D neutronic toolset used at Framatome for VVER's core analysis, using the OECD/NEA Rostov-2 benchmark specification.

In the research, three numerical approaches were tested. The first one consists of the HELIOS/DYN3D toolchain dedicated to VVER's neutronic calculations. The second assumed the preparation of a detailed 3D core model with Serpent to obtain the reference results, and the last was to test the Serpent ability to generate two-group constants which then can be applied for simulations with the DYN3D core simulator. The research focuses on the power distribution comparative analysis in hot zero power

steady-state involving radial assembly and pin power distribution, as well as axial power distribution. Comparison of all three solutions was performed and presents overall good agreement.

Considering radial assembly-wise power distribution, it can be noticed that with HELIOS/DYN3D and Serpent/DYN3D, the results for central FAs and some outer FAs are lower than the results obtained with Serpent, and vice versa for the middle-ring of FAs in the core, where Serpent gives lower values. In case of pin power distribution, it is hard to point out similarly the specific pattern, where values obtained with one code are higher or lower compared to the other. For most of the pins, the absolute difference shows good agreement and is below 0.002. However, for the pins with the highest absolute difference, a systematic overestimation by Serpent, or underestimation by HELIOS/DYN3D and Serpent/DYN3D should be considered. Analyzing the axial power distribution, it can be noticed that results of HELIOS/DYN3D and Serpent/DYN3D calculations, compared to Serpent, show higher values in the top of the core, and lower in the bottom part. However, comparing those codes to each other, HELIOS/DYN3D indicates higher results in the top and bottom core layers, and lower in the center.

Further analysis including the determination of the spacer grid model impact on the radial and axial power distribution is under investigation.

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